

IDENTIFY THE FACTORS WHICH EFFECTS ON QUALITY OF NURSING CARE AT ALLIED HOSPITAL FAISALABAD, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

The present study investigates the factors affecting the quality of nursing care at Allied Hospital Faisalabad, Pakistan. Nursing care plays a central role in the development of healthcare services, influenced by factors such as reducing stress, nurse workload, noise pollution, shortage of nurses, lack of facilities, and proper patient-nurse communication. A descriptive cross-sectional technique was employed, using a random sample of 236 participants collected through a questionnaire. The quality of nursing care was rated as excellent by 57.62%, good by 38.13%, and poor by 4.23%. Health factors linked with care showed similar results, with 53.38% rating it as excellent. Factors such as patient satisfaction, environmental conditions (e.g., noise and cleanliness), and administrative support were also found to significantly impact care quality. Cleanliness of facilities and reducing noise pollution were linked to improved patient outcomes. The study concluded that Allied Hospital Faisalabad provides better quality of nursing care compared to other government hospitals, with overall assessments highlighting the need to address stress reduction, workload, and environmental improvements for further enhancing care quality.

INTRODUCTION

Satisfaction with nursing care is the best indicator of patient satisfaction with health care. First experience with watching their expectations as satisfaction with care, and hospice care behaviors can be affected by several factors [1]. The multiple welfares were played the central role for the enhancement of quality of nursing care in different hospitals. Everyone know about the nursing care was used to improve the patients satisfaction level. The Deen and Lin is the modern researcher in '1996' both of them provided the information about care factors were calculated by applying the following parameters such as structure, process and outcomes. The better health of the client (patient) improved the market value of the organization and also enhances the business related to medical services. Moreover, the quality of nursing

care depends upon the multiple technical components like services, user-friendliness and capability of nurses [2]. The experience patients are played the vital role to identify the quality of nursing and estimate the ranking for healthcare organizations [3]. The service delivery is the major parameter for patient satisfaction and the growth of organization depends upon the patient's satisfaction. Recently, the healthcare problems are the main challenging task especially in Pakistan and if the multiple organizations are proper performed [4]. The qualities of nurses are numerous discipline concepts in these days. The essential factor for quality of nursing care such as client satisfaction and beneficial for health care organization [5]. The huge number of parameters is not suitable for healthcare

service and stops the growth rate of the country economy like high cost treatment, low quality hospital facilities, communication gap, non-satisfaction client and lack of nurses. In early days nurses personally focus on healthcare service in community hospitals [6]. In these days, to increase the work load of nurses and lack of information about the health care services are the challenging task for the client. The medical researchers reported that the quality of infrastructure, operational system, training and competence level of nursing also used to enhance quality of care level [7]. The patients care is possible only if the nursing satisfied about the proper care standard in medical organization. Presently, need to improve the both medical and nonmedical staff related to link with care of both patient and nurses. It was reported that the developed countries focus to overcome the different challenges related to care about client and nursing [8]. The communication factor represents the vital impact on care service of clients and nurses. Recently, it was need to reduce the miss understanding barrier (geography, language and economy) between staff members and young nurses [9]. At that time the world health organization (WHO) was played the central role to improve the health care service especially in Pakistan. In Pakistan the health care service like very poor and careless facilities are provided in different government hospitals. Globally, the developed countries such as United States of America (USA), Australia, Norway, Switzerland, Ireland, Hong Kong, China, Sweden and Mexico were provided the four dimension parameters like expert medical staff, excellent infrastructure, good social service and easy accessibility.

1.2 Objectives of Study

- 1: To highlights the main factors of nursing care in Allied Hospital Faisalabad.
- 2: To highlight the factors are suitable for patient's satisfaction.
- 3: To highlight the factors are beneficial for health organization sectors.
- 4: To highlight the factors are suitable to improve the behavior of nurses with patients.

1. Literature Review

This review provided the main discussion about the four major steps are discuss in this frame work of study such as environmental, nurses, patients and organization factors. Furthermore, the initial step was enclosed the research of different researchers work on the quality of nursing care particularly in Allied hospital Faisalabad.

(Ramzan et al., 2024) studied about the Increase the work stress which effect on physically and mentally health of nurse's causes to increase the number of patients. This study was also related to identify the depression, non-satisfaction and mental stress factors [10]. The descriptive method was used to complete this task in medical emergency of Allied Hospital FSD and the data analysis software was used SPSS-20. The young nurses in the age of 25-35 years were preferred for this task and it was observed that 72% nurses in mental stress problems due to management of the hospital. It was conclude that the nurses patient increase in Allied Hospital day by day due to mental stress [11].

(Sadaf et al., 2018) provided the analysis about the healthcare service was improved to focus on the following factors such as hospital facilities, reduce the communication gap, patient satisfaction and complete the staff members. This study was related to Allied hospital in Faisalabad and some of the parameters were observed to reduce the health of the patients like more burdens of the work on nurses, unfortunate behavior with patients. It was reported that different organization need to work on the heath care service through video channels and arrange multiple lecture for nurses to improve the health care service of allied hospital. Furthermore, the administration of the allied hospital was used to reduce the noise, communication gap and remove the problems related to cleanness [12].

(Shabbir, S., & Inayat, 2017) reported that the different health care organizations were worked for the improvement of patient satisfaction. After the improvement of this factor, it was not properly regards at that time due to lack of information about the proper service quality. This study was provided the complete awareness of the healthcare service to the nurses especially in Allied hospital, Faisalabad. To complete this task was used descriptive method and questionnaire related to administration of allied

hospital, Faisalabad. Moreover, the 248 well educated nurses were decided as a sample size and non-satisfactory factor of patients (76.6%) due to small quantity of employees, lack of information, low quality apparatus and lack of facilities. Finally, improved the health care service by enhance the following factors such as full fill the employees capacity, proper communication between patients, administration and nurses [13].

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGYS

3.1 Study Area

This study was carried out especially in Allied Hospital Faisalabad, because it is national Hospital of Pakistan. The Allied Hospital is the main hospital of the Faisalabad district. This study was completed in medical and surgical wards of the Allied Hospital. The choice of Allied Hospital is that because it is crowded Government Hospital of Pakistan. This is the best place to investigate the factor of quality of nursing care in Hospital.

3.2 Target Population

The populations of the hospital including the management staff, wards boys and patients are central person used to investigate and identified the factor of quality of nursing care. The quality of nursing care was calculated to collect the feedback of all the patients admit inside the surgical and medical words of the Allied Hospital of Pakistan.

3.3 Sample Size

The Kish and Leslie formula was more famous in medical field was used to calculate the sample size of multiple studies [14]. The preferred studies sample size was calculated by using this method. The mathematical expression of required formula can be expressed as:

$$N = \frac{q^2 \times p(1-p)}{d^2} \dots\dots\dots (i)$$

Here, notation expression used in equation (i) such as N= Sample size, q = Z value always equal to 1.96, p = Complication factor about care service, d = Occurrence error percentage (%) By applying this relation was used to calculate the sample size is equal to 236. Which was involved the patients, staff workers and young nurses of the Allied Hospital FSD.

3.4 Sampling Technique

The multiple sampling techniques were used to investigate the factor of quality of care. But here the random sampling method was adopted on daily basis to investigate the nursing care factor [15]. The one working days visit to the medical and surgical emergency and provided the questionnaire performa to each patients and properly guide about it. After guidance the patients complete the performa and this process repeat for multiple patients admit in medical and surgical wards. After that the same process was also applied to the management's staff provided the performa and guided about the purpose of study then after some times the filled questionnaire performa was collected back. Furthermore, if the one patient is failed to contribution in study then more toward next patents. By applying this process to all questionnaires performa was completed.

3.2 Research Tool for Data Collection

3.2.1 Data Collection Techniques

The questionnaire is the main research tool was adopted to complete the novel work [16]. The initial step was used to collect the data through questionnaire performa. All the questionnaire performa were distributed to respondents (patients and managements of the hospitals). Furthermore, all the information available inside the performa linked to the factor like quality of nursing care. The guideline of the questionnaire performa was added with the help of supervisor and expert of the medical field especially linked with quality of nursing care factors. The interviews guide was also developed with the help of multiple health workers and discuss about the quantitative data about the quality of nursing care with the help of different patents linked with surgical and medical wards of the Allied Hospital Faisalabad. Finally, the filled questionnaire performa provided the group's members to generate qualitative data about care [17].

3.2.2 Interviews

The interview means developed the face to face connection between researcher nurses and respondents. This is the simplest methods was used to controlled the factors such as flexibility and time [18]. After reading the questionnaire performa then

the every person understand the proper information about quality of care.

3.3 Data Processing System

3.3.1 Quality Control Factor

The required questionnaires performa were completed before 4 week to collect the data about quality of care. Moreover, all the researchers worked together and properly handle all the patients and save the data. The proper method was used to collect the data because the proper methods used to reduce the error in required data [19]. The multiple factors are discussed in dependent variable and independent variable which involved was used to complete this task.

3.3.2 Coding Factor

The coding was used to arrange the data in the form of different classes and groups. These multiples class was used to plot the graph between dependent and independent variable to investigate the multiple factors especially nursing care factor [20].

3.3.3 Cleaning Factor

The cleaning factor was used to reduce the error occur inside the data and it was also used to calculate the accuracy factor. Moreover, the invalid values were removed from the collected data and adding the mission value inside the required data [21].

3.3.4 Data Analysis Factor

Daily basis the question on questionnaires performa was calculated and required question response added in another sheet. After collected the response of every question then SSP program was used to differentiate the uni, bi and multivariate values. Finally, the statistic analysis was used to calculate the square and P-value factors. The complex data analysis was used to calculate the uni and multivariate methods.

3.4 Ethical Issues

Without the permission of medical superintendent then the research work was not completed especially related to medical center [22]. So this study was completed with the permission of medical superintendent and no ethical issue was take place to complete to this task was done in Allied Hospital Faisalabad. Moreover, the entire interview was collected of the entire person in separate room in Allied Hospital Faisalabad Pakistan.

3.5 Limitations

The following are the limitation was used to complete the research work.

- The few patients avoids to completing the questionnaire performa because he affair about the different difficulty take place inside the ward.
- This study cannot complete outside the Allied Hospital Faisalabad.
- To correct information provided inside the thesis and cannot provided the fake data.

4: DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Enclosed the finding of quality of care and represent the data was presented in tables and expressed in the form of graph such as pi charts etc. The required data manipulate and statistical analysis was provided to calculate most effected square values. Finally, this chapter was provided the information of quality of care linked with environmental, organizational, Nursing and patients related factors.

4.1 Distribution of Patients (Medical and Surgical Ward)

The 236 are the sample size of all the participants were contributed in both medical and surgical wards. The 50% interview was performed in medical ward and remaining 50% interview were collected from surgical ward. The collected data was plotted in the form of pi chart as shown in figure (4.1):

Figure (4.1) shows the equal number of participants inside both medical and surgical wards

Table 4.1: Shows the graphic Characteristics of all the Participants

Distribution of graphic characteristics expression			
Characteristics	Category	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Sex	Female	170	72.0334
	Male	66	27.9661
Age	25-30	50	21.1864
	30-35	90	38.1355
	35-40	96	40.6779
Education	Primary	78	33.0508
	Bachelor	115	48.7288
	Master	43	18.2203
Occupation	Self employed	109	46.1864
	Civil servant	86	36.4406
	Casual	41	17.3728

The table (4.1) indicated that the majority female participants (72.0334%) and minority male (27.9661%), the mostly participant belong to the age group range 35-40 years old. The few parameters are used inside the table here expressed the proper meaning linked with studies such as:

- Poor (The participant have small information about question)
- Good (The participant have intermediate information about question)
- Excellent (The participant have more information about question)

Table 4.2: Factor Affecting Quality of Care

Scores of total participant (236) and their percentages (%)				
Questions	Poor	Good	Excellent	Total
Do you know about quality of care?	10(4.23)	90(38.13)	136(57.62)	236(100)
Quality of care affects on health.	35(14.83)	75(31.77)	126(53.38)	236(100)
Quality of care is affected by short staffing.	15(6.35)	149(63.13)	72(30.50)	236(100)
Are you satisfied with quality of care was provided in Allied Hospital Faisalabad?	35(14.83)	100(42.37)	101(42.79)	236(100)
Health care administrators should elaborate for proper staffing for providing quality care of patient.	45(19.06)	93(39.40)	98(41.52)	236(100)

Table (4.2) represents the factor effecting quality of care especially in Allied Hospital Faisalabad. Table (4.2) indicates the factor of quality of care poor 4.23%, good 38.13% and excellent 57.62%. It is clearly shows that the quality of nursing care factor provided the excellent results only 57.62% then nursing need to improve the quality of care. Furthermore, the poor impression is very low nearly equal to 4.23%. Finally, the administrators provided the care to the staffing member's represent the percentage factors excellent 41.52%, good 39.40% and poor 19.06%. This factor represents the intermediate expression so the different organization need to work on these multiples factors then the value and economy level of the hospital increased.

Table 4.3: Nurses related Factor about Quality of Care

Scores of total participant (236) and their percentages (%)				
Questions	Poor	Good	Excellent	Total
Over burden has influence on staff Nurse behaviour?	19(8.05)	115(48.72)	102(43.22)	236(100)
Quality of care and patient satisfaction are considered the most crucial point in nursing assessment?	25(10.59)	61(25.84)	150(63.55)	236(100)
Quality of care and patient satisfaction is the key elements in health care system?	0(0.00)	100(42.37)	136(57.62)	236(100)
Patient receives good quality of nursing care then it can be lead to their long life?	5(2.11)	131(55.50)	100(42.37)	236(100)
Behavior of staff Nurse affects on quality of care?	3(1.27)	136(57.62)	97(41.10)	236(100)

Table (4.3) shows the nurse's related factors of quality of care and these questions provided the information about the nursing care factors. To increase the burden on the nursing then the taking behaviors of the nursing was completely changed. The majority factor is expressed, which indicate the percentage excellent 43.22%, good 48.72% and poor 8.05%. The percentage expression shows that to increase the burden on the nurses then the nurses face the difficulties.

Table 4.4: Patients related Factor about Quality of Nursing Care

Scores of total participant (236) and their percentages (%)				
Questions	Poor	Good	Excellent	Total
Are you satisfied with quality of care which patient receives?	12(5.08)	76(32.20)	148(62.71)	236(100)
Over burden of patients affects on providing quality of nursing care.	32(13.55)	105(44.49)	99(41.94)	236(100)
Are you satisfied the facilities which	3(1.27)	145(61.44)	88(37.28)	236(100)

provided to patients in government hospital?				
A trained person is required for providing best quality of care to patients?	7(2.96)	54(22.88)	175(74.15)	236(100)
The nurse fulfill the necessary requirements is applied to patients.	11(4.66)	90(38.13)	135(57.20)	236(100)

Table (4.4) represents the patient’s related factors; the patients are the main factor was used to increase the economy level of the hospital. The initial statement represent the satisfaction level of the patients how receive inside the hospital. The percentage factor about the satisfaction level of the treatment represents excellent 62.71%, good 32.20% and 5.08%. The different organization need to provide information, how to enhance the satisfaction level of the patients

Discussion

The study highlights that the quality of nursing care in Allied Hospital Faisalabad can be significantly improved by addressing several factors. Key issues include the burden on nurses, which affects their behavior, and the need for better hospital facilities, such as reducing congestion in wards and improving cleanliness. Patient satisfaction is crucial for enhancing the quality of care, and addressing environmental factors like noise pollution and hospital conditions can contribute positively. The findings suggest that if these factors are managed effectively, the quality of nursing care and patient outcomes can both be enhanced.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study conducted in Allied Hospital Faisalabad, Pakistan, emphasizes that quality nursing care is crucial for improving hospital performance and patient outcomes. Key factors affecting quality care include patient satisfaction, stress reduction, nurse workload, and environmental issues like noise pollution and cleanliness. The findings indicate that controlling these factors can significantly enhance the quality of care, with patient satisfaction being a central indicator. The study also reveals that Allied Hospital provides better treatment compared to other government hospitals in Pakistan. Addressing staff shortages, improving facilities, and fostering effective communication between patients and nurses are critical for further improving care quality.

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